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A Study on the Benefits of Yoga Practices

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Abstract:

Yoga is a spiritual discipline that originated in ancient India, focusing on harmonizing the body, mind, and spirit through physical postures (asanas), breath control (pranayama), and meditation. Yoga's incorporation of meditation and breathing can help improve a person's mental well-being.

The exact origin of Yoga is uncertain but collecting the small pieces together takes us to a valid conclusion. It is said that Yoga originated into the west and the first sign appeared in ancient Shamanism that date back to some 3000 B.C. Evidence of Yoga can also be found in Rig Veda.

Introduction:

Yoga is a spiritual discipline that originated in ancient India, focusing on harmonizing the body, mind, and spirit through physical postures (*asanas*), breath control (*pranayama*), and meditation. Yoga's incorporation of meditation and breathing can help improve a person's mental well-being. "Regular yoga practice creates mental clarity and calmness; increases body awareness; relieves chronic stress patterns; relaxes the mind; centers attention; and sharpens concentration". The aim of this paper is to explore how yoga is beneficial for health to see the goodness of yoga for improving health and decrease the chances of diseases.

Need of the Study:

Yoga is certainly more than mastering its postures and asanas and increasing the strength and flexibility of body. It indicates towards healing of mind and body and attaining the state of self enlightenment. It is said that in early periods when Yoga was just introduced, the main purpose was to heal community members and the practitioners act as religious mediators. The exact origin of Yoga is uncertain but collecting the small pieces together takes us to a valid conclusion. It is said that Yoga originated into the west and the first sign appeared in ancient Shamanism that date back to some 3000 B.C. Evidence of Yoga can also be found in Rig Veda.

The word Yoga provides a sense of peace which certainly derived from the etymology of the word. The word has been taken from the Sanskrit word 'Yuj' which means unite or join. This word unite has been taken in the sense of uniting the individual with cosmic consciousness. The main purpose of practicing Yoga is to taking control over the body, mind and emotional aspects. The cessation of bad thoughts creates a positive vibe around the person and makes him healthy overall.

Importance of Yoga Practices:

In Indian civilization and culture, yoga occupies a highly esteemed place, from time immemorial. In the ancient times, the practitioner of yoga was regarded thousand times superior to the house-holder and the celibate, and hundred times superior to the hermit. Because of its importance felt by the people in different ages, the practice of yoga is being continued since the pre-historic days to the present day. Day by day, its importance and popularity is increasing, and now, it has become a universal phenomenon.

Our worldly lives are always full of pain and suffering. We give in our endless efforts in order to gain or overcome relief from such sufferings and also to gain happiness. And as a result of our efforts, pleasure comes to our lives, although for a temporary period. The universal importance of yoga lies in the fact that its regular practice with sincerity and devotion drives away worldly pains and sufferings for good and the practitioner enjoys permanent peace and bliss.

Major Benefits of Yoga Practices- “Physical and Mental”:

- Improves lung capacity
- Relieves anxiety
- Relieves chronic back pain
- Lowers blood sugar in diabetics
- Improves brain function
- Alters gene expression
- A Drop in The Pulse Rate
- Increases Strength
- Anxiety Management
- Better Cardiovascular Endurance
- Increases flexibility
- Lowers blood pressure
- Improves sense of balance
- Stronger bones
- Healthy weight
- Lowers risk of heart diseases
- Lowered Respiratory Rate
- Fights Depression
- Teaches Balance
- Stimulation of Organs

Conclusion:

In the present-day world, the diseases of psycho-somatic origin, such as hyper-tension, heart-diseases, asthma, diabetes, insomnia are increasing very fast and the modern medical science has failed to cure these diseases. After a lot of scientific experiments done on patients undergoing yogic treatment, it has been found to be the most effective treatment for all these ailments.

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